

PECULIARITIES OF ELECTRIC POWER ENGINEERING TERMS FORMATION

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Abstract. The paper describes main ways of terms formation in the field of power engineering as this field of study has great potential for future development (renewable energy sources). The aim of this research was to investigate structure and processes involved into the terms building. The prevailing amount of them is constituted by multicomponent terms and terminological phrases. Morphological formation is the most widespread way of terms building. Another important detail regarding complex engineering terms is an attribute cluster.

Keywords: terms formation, translation, terminological phrase, neologisms, power engineering

INTRODUCTION

In the modern world of scientific and technical literature where translators are often challenged with innovative texts containing descriptions of novel technologies, new scientific findings, new intellectual insights, etc. that unavoidably contain new terms (or changed meanings of existing terms), they are expected to coin and propose corresponding new terms in the target language. This process of language innovation is governed by a multitude of socio-cultural factors that determine the role of language in a particular society or language community, the cognitive factors of accepting new terms, etc. It is well known that every technical text comprises subject-field-specific terminology (often from different domains). A term is an integrative part of a lexical system of any language. Terms are also distinguished

from other word categories by their enormous informational connotation. However, regarding translation, the term is considered to be one of the main challenges due to its sophisticated structure and possible polysemy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this paper we will be studying terminology in the sphere of electric power engineering. Firstly, this sphere has great potential for future development (renewable energy sources). Secondly, the analysis of the materials has shown that translators face certain challenges in identifying and translating professional and highly specialized vocabulary. Moreover, the following term analysis will be useful both for translation as well as for linguistics because it reveals the main structures deployed for terms formation.

Thus, there the following objectives of our study:

- to study the literature covering the issue stated in this study;
- to analyze main methods of terms formation;
- to investigate the challenges rising while translating;
- to consider peculiarities of neologisms and their characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the main requirement to the term is its uniqueness, this requirement is implemented in two possible ways as there are two types of terms: 1) general scientific and technical terms, 2) special (nomenclature) terms. General scientific and technical terms express the general concepts of science and technology. Terms exist not only in the language, but in certain terminology system. Terminology as the system of scientific terms is a subsystem within a general lexical system. According to A.A. Reformatskiy (2010), terminology is a system of scientific concepts corresponding to the appropriate verbal expression. If the in general language (not within the terminology) the word can be polysemantic, then within the framework of the certain terminology, it becomes monosemantic. This statement is

very important in terms of further analysis which will reveal the nature of terms formation in power engineering.

Specific character of terms as a special category of lexical words is that they are created in the process of production and research and therefore operate only within the environment which contains corresponding scientific and industrial realities, i.e. macro-context. Therefore, in contrast to general words, whose meaning becomes evident through the situation or linguistic context, the monosemy of the term is regulated by both extralinguistic macro-context and linguistic micro-context.

The term does not require a context, as a general word does since it 1) is a member of a specific terminology that substitutes the context; 2) may be used independently, for example, in lists, registers or orders, and 3) it should be monosemantic not in the general language but within the terminology where it is used.

The accuracy of a term must be seen as its ability to reflect as far as possible the features that are provided in the definition. A term should be concise because if it is too long it will be violating the principle of linguistic economy. Moreover, it can lead to omission which can cause incorrect translation and misunderstanding.

In scientific and technical terminology such linguistic phenomena as polysemy, synonymy, homonymy may result in misunderstandings and above that rather severe translation mistakes. Therefore, before creating a new term for the concept several factors should be taken into account: first of all, a profound linguistic study should prove that there is no existing term in the language for the concept and secondly, if there are several synonymous terms for the concept the term which fulfills the maximal number of requirements should be approved.

New terms can be formed in a certain environment, e.g. in a research laboratory, in an industrial company, at a conference, etc. Usually, a term is formed within the subject field in which it will be used; it is conditioned by the personal features of the persons involved, by the stimulus causing the term emerging, and of

course, by the phonological, morpho- syntactical and lexical structures of the language in which the new concept finds its linguistic expression.

In the sphere of science and technology, particularly in electric and power engineering fields, multicomponent terms form more than 80% of the entire word stock. This tendency finds its reflection in numerous multicomponent terminological combinations, such as e.g. power-flow-type relay, capacitor-compensated transmission line, secondary grid-type distribution system etc.

Word borrowings from other languages are negligible in this point of consideration, since these lexical units do not exceed 3-4%. Suffixation is the most common type of morphological word formation; 5-18% of terms are formed this way. Current English scientific and technical literature is characterized by an increasing number of various contractions (abbreviations) among all morphological word classes and combinations as well as by formation of new words via contraction of the existing ones (today there are more than 250 000 abbreviations registered in Romanized countries).

This is a result of communication informational optimization and reveals a tendency to minimize complicated signs, e.g.:

VAR – Volt-Ampere-reactive;

RMS – root-mean-square;

EMF – electro-motive force;

STATCOM – Static Synchronous Compensator;

SVC – Static VAR compensator;

TCR – Thyristor Controlled Reactor;

TSR – Thyristor Switched Reactor;

MSC – Mechanically Switched Capacitor

ALNICO – Aluminum-Nickel-Cobalt alloy.

Attributive clusters as a main method of terms formation become more and more widespread in practice. This is reasoned by external factors. First of all, any

language has a limited amount of lexical units. Secondly, the results of scientific and technical revolution have led to new discoveries and phenomena which require specific definitions and nominations.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of terms formation depends on the type of a term and is defined by the number of components, and this in its turn defines a terminological phrase. Terminological phrase allows to compress the information and to form inter-phrase ties between sentences and paragraphs in scientific and technical texts.

Formation analysis of English power engineering terms leads to the conclusion that the main ways of their formation are syntactic, semantic and morphological, they can be also built through the borrowings from other languages and special-field terminology. Most of the contemporary English terms have syntactical origin.

REFERENCES

1. Alekseeva, I. S., (2014). Professional translator training. Moscow: Galperin I. R., (2017). Stylistics. Moscow: Higher School.
2. Gerding-Salas, C., (2020). Teaching Translation // Translation Journal. Volume 4, No. 3.
3. Hann, M. (2012). The Key to Technical Translation. Volume 1: Concept specification. John Benjamins Publishing Company, pp. 248 p.